

7th Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Symposium (IBICS-7)

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Organising Committee: Joseph P. Byrne (Chair),^a Susan Quinn,^a Andrew Phillips^a, Sophie Kavanagh^a

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Organisation: Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society

Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, Mason Technology, GPE/Julabo, Merck, Accuscience.

Summary

The 7th annual symposium of the **Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS)** was held for the first time in **UCD** just before Christmas. IBICS organises an annual symposium, bringing together scientists and experts from universities and industries active in the field of bioinorganic chemistry. The programme was split into three sessions with 12 talks, covering different key themes throughout including but not limited to DNA targeting and sensing, anti-cancer complexes and metallodrugs against microbes. The symposium included two plenary lectures from Professor Ramon Villar (Imperial College London, UK) Professor Petra Heffeter (Medical University of Vienna, Austria), as well as two invited speakers Professor Denise Rooney (Maynooth University) and Professor Mathias Senge (Trinity College Dublin). The bulk of the programme gave opportunities for oral and flash presentations by early-stage researchers, while sixteen posters from universities all over Ireland formed the basis of discussion during the day-long event. This symposium gave IBICS members opportunities to present research to peers and hosted the Society's

AGM. The day featured two poster sessions and wrapped up with a wine reception. Networking was an integral part of this event, allowing participants to share their passion for chemistry while also learning from accomplished experts in the field.

Attendees

The event's 87 delegates included postgraduate and academic researchers, and industrial exhibitors working in areas of inorganic chemistry, microbiology and life sciences, who together contributed to a wonderful inclusive atmosphere and highly enjoyable meeting. The majority of delegates were academics, postdocs and graduate students. The gender breakdown of delegates was approximately 40:60 female:male, with the programme of speakers also reflecting this, balancing male and female plenary and invited speakers, with a slight imbalance in contributed talks, reflecting the asymmetry of the delegate gender balance.

Target audience: Academics, Early Career (Academia), Industrialists, Postgraduates

Programme

The symposium took place over a full day, and the programme (Table 1) consisted of two international plenary speakers, two invited speakers from Ireland, a postgraduate award lecture, seven contributed oral presentations, seven flash presentations, and sixteen posters. The latter categories were mostly contributions from early career researchers, representing most universities in the Republic of Ireland. The AGM of IBICS also took place during the programme, as well as several networking sessions. Posters were displayed over two sessions, one during the lunch break and again during a dedicated hour-long session during the afternoon, which was sponsored by the RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section.

Early-career scientists from most Irish universities applied to speak and a balance was aimed for to represent the diversity of work happening across the country through inclusion of speakers from different institutions. Sessions were chaired by national leaders in the field of bioinorganic chemistry, Dr Ronconi, Dr Phillips, Dr Quinn and Prof. Marmion.

Proceedings

Session 1: Chair Dr Luca Ronconi

Professor **Ramon Vilar** (Imperial College London) opened IBICS-7 with a *plenary lecture* on targeting DNA with luminescent metal complexes. Prof Vilar is Professor of Medicinal Inorganic Chemistry and Vice Dean for Research at the Faculty of Natural

Sciences. In his lecture, he focussed on non-canonical DNA structures, in particular guanine-quadruplex DNA, which have been identified as attractive anticancer drug targets. He presented results from his lab on

imaging these DNA structures in cells and how light can be used to modulate and control the cellular properties of small molecules.

Continuing the theme of DNA sensing, **Maria Byrne** (Susan Quinn Group, UCD)

delivered the first oral presentation of the morning, describing multi-emissive silica nanomaterials as sensors which bind DNA. She reported encapsulation of ruthenium polypyridyl complexes into SiO₂ nanoparticles and exploration of their sensing properties, including considerations for functionalising the surface of the nanoparticles with luminescent DNA probes.

Table 1. Programme of IBICS-7

Time	Speaker and title of presentation
10:00	Registration, coffee, and poster setup
10:30	Opening remarks: Professor Michael Devereaux, IBICS President
Session 1, Chair: Dr Luca Ronconi	
10:40	Plenary: Professor Ramon Vilar (Imperial College London) "Targeting DNA with luminescent metal complexes – imaging and therapy"
11:20	Maria Byrne (University College Dublin): "Multi Emissive Silica Nanomaterials for DNA Sensing"
11:35	Rhianne Curley (Dublin City University): "Exploring the Efficacy of a Mitochondrial G4-Targeted Ruthenium(II) Complex in Cell Monolayers and Multicellular Tumour Spheroids"
11:50	Invited: Professor Denise Rooney (Maynooth University): "Medicinal Applications of Transition Metal Coordination Complexes of N-Based Heterocyclic Derivatives"
12:20	Flash Session, Chair: Dr Andrew Phillips 3-minute talks, sponsored by Institute of Chemistry of Ireland
12:35	Lunch (provided) and Poster Session 1
13:25	IBICS Annual General Meeting
Session 2, Chair: Prof Susan Quinn	
13:55	Invited: Professor Mathias Senge (Trinity College Dublin): "On Trial: The Case of Aluminum Dipyrinato Photosensitizers"
12:35	Simon Poole (Dublin City University): "The Generation of a New Class of Click Chemistry-Derived Dinuclear Copper(II) Artificial Metalloenzyme"
14:40	Darren Beirne (Maynooth University): "Pt(IV)-Sunitinib pro-drug conjugates displaying promising preliminary anti-cancer activity"
14:55	Lewis More O'Ferrall (RSCl and TU Dublin): "Ga(III) siderophore complexes - A Metallo-Trojan Horse Strategy to tackle Aspergillus fumigatus lung infections"
15:10	Ella O'Sullivan (TU Dublin): "Investigating Apoptosis Induction as a Mechanism of Action of Novel Metal-Dicarboxylate-Phenanthroline Complexes"
15:40	Poster Session 2, sponsored by RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section
Session 3, Chair: Prof Celine Marmion	
16:40	Dr Neville Murphy (University of Galway): "Intracellular behaviour of metallacarboranes through the lens of stimulated Raman spectroscopy"
16:55	Plenary: Professor Petra Heffeter (Medical University of Vienna) "Development of new strategies to overcome the therapeutic limitations of inorganic anticancer drugs"
17:35	Presentation of IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal Dr Amir Abdo (CÚRAM/University of Galway) "Metalloporphyrins as Potential Nitric Oxide Scavengers for treatment of breast cancer"
17:55	Prize-giving and closing remarks by Professor Michael Devereaux
18:00	Wine reception

Rhianne Curley (Tia Keyes Group, DCU) presented the *in vitro* behaviour of ruthenium complexes targeting mitochondrial guanine quadruplexes in cell mono-

layers, and multi-cellular tumour spheroids. The complexes effectively targeted mitochondrial DNA and demonstrated light-activated therapeutic activity in both normoxic and hypoxic cellular environments.

Professor **Denise Rooney** (Maynooth University) concluded the morning session with an *invited talk*, presenting an overview encompassing years of collaborative research across several groups in the Irish bioinorganic community focussing on the antimicrobial activity of silver complexes of phenanthroline derivatives and their potential against bacteria and fungi (such as *C. albicans*). Additionally, recent results with rhenium and iron carbonyl complexes with *N*-heterocycles and their medicinal applications were presented, including their role as CO-releasing molecules.

Flash Presentations: Chair Dr Andrew Phillips

Before lunch, there was an opportunity for seven early career researchers (Figure 1) to present their work in the form of rapid-fire flash presentations. The flash session was sponsored by the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland. Joshua Thorogood was awarded the ICI Flash Prize for his work on Synthetic Magnesium Tetrapyrrole Radicals to understand the mechanisms behind the redox potential of chlorophyll-*a* in P680.

Poster Session 1

Two poster sessions were included in the Symposium Programme, the first over the lunch break and the second in the mid-afternoon. This was to ensure that adequate time was given to delegates to discuss research with the early-career researchers, make connections, and potentially fuel future collaborations. Posters were presented by Sachidulal Biswas (TCD), Federica Brescia (University of Galway), Agnideep Das (TCD), Clara Evans (Maynooth University), Judit Fodor (TCD), Daniel Graczyk (UCD), Sophie Kavanagh & Thomas Rabbittie (UCD), Agnieszka Kawalerska (TU Dublin), Oscar Kelly (TCD), Darragh McHugh (University

of Galway), Phillip Morgenfurt (DCU), Joshua Thorogood (TCD), Kaja Turzanska (RCSI), Eleanor Windle (UCD), Karolina Wojtczak (University of Galway) and Clara Zehe (UCD).

Figure 1. Flash presenters: Clara Evans (MU), Joshua Thorogood (TCD), Thomas Rabbittie (UCD) Phillip Morgenfurt (DCU) Federica Brescia (UoG), Eleanor Windle (UCD) and Agnideep Das (TCD);

IBICS Annual General Meeting

As part of the AGM, held after lunch, Prof. Mick Devereaux's term as President ended, and Dr Luca Ronconi from University of Galway was elected the incoming President of the Society. Prof. Orla Howe (TU Dublin) was elected Vice-President for the coming year. It was also announced that the 8th IBICS Symposium will be held in University College Cork next year, chaired by Dr Christopher Burke. Some members of the IBICS Committee are photographed in Figure 2–3.

Figure 2. Members of the IBICS Committee: Christopher Burke (UCC), Joseph Byrne (UCD), Deirdre Fitzgerald-Hughes (RCSI), Celine Marmion (RCSI), Michael Devereaux (TUD, outgoing President), Bernie Creaven (TUD), Orla Howe (TUD), Luca Ronconi (UoG, incoming President)

Session 2: Chair Professor Susan Quinn

Resuming the scientific programme, Professor **Mathias Senge** (Trinity College Dublin) delivered an *engaging invited talk*, in the style of a court case: "On Trial: The Case of Aluminium Dipyrinato Photosensitizers", where he made the case for the use of abundant and inexpensive aluminium in *tris*-dipyrinato complexes for potential photodynamic therapy applications. He

Figure 3. Attendees at Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Symposium and Annual General Meeting

Figure 4. Chairing various sessions of the Symposium, from top left: Professor Michael Devereaux, Dr Joseph Byrne, Dr Luca Ronconi, Dr Andrew Phillips, Professor Susan Quinn, Professor Celine Marmion.

gave a historical overview of “heliotherapy”, properties of porphyrins and BODIPY derivatives before describing a library of aluminium compounds, their absorbance and fluorescence with triplet excited state lifetimes with potential for acceptable singlet oxygen production. Prof Senge was pleased to be invited to the meeting as an “outsider” (an organic chemist) and the talk was very well received.

Simon Poole (Andrew Kellett Group, DCU) reported the generation of a new class of ‘click’ chemistry-derived dinuclear copper(II) artificial metallonuclease. These compounds were designed as new anticancer agents to overcome resistance, causing long-range crosslinking interactions in DNA which circumvent typical DNA adduct repair processes. He presented a library of triazole-linked complexes and detailed the structure-activity relationship study which gave rise to a lead compound with promising selectivity against cancer.

Darren Beirne (Maynooth University) described Pt(IV) pro-drugs based on sunitinib derivatives of FDA-approved Pt(II) metallodrugs (cisplatin, oxaliplatin and carboplatin) and their potential for overcoming limitations of existing chemotherapies. These compounds were designed to target tyrosine kinases, which play a major role in cell regulation pathways. The presentation included promising preliminary anti-cancer activity against several cell lines.

Lewis More O’Ferrall (Groups of Darren Griffith, RCSI and Christine O’Connor, TU Dublin), told the Symposium about developments in gallium(III) siderophore derivatives, which work as a metallo-Trojan horse strategy to tackle *Aspergillus fumigatus* and take advantage of microbes’ high demand for Fe(III), highlighting the issue of antimicrobial resistance

and persistent lower respiratory tract infections. He described their new treatment and its various formulations suitable for lung delivery, along with the Ga(III) complex selective toxicity to *A. fumigatus*. These treatments, non toxic to human cells, were more effective than simple Ga(III) complexes.

Ella O’Sullivan (Orla Howe Group, TU Dublin) began her talk, highlighting the unprecedented increase in cancer incidence and detailing anti-cancer potential of a range of Cu(II), Mn(II) and Ag(I) complexes incorporating bridging dicarboxylate and chelating 1,10-phenanthroline ligands. Her talk focussed on elucidating differing cytotoxic mechanisms of the complexes against various cell lines, with some demonstrating antioxidant effects and others generating intracellular ROS. The role of apoptosis in regulated cell death caused by the complexes was profiled by various methods.

Poster Session 2

This session was sponsored by the Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section. Over the course of an hour, the poster presenters mingled with other delegates (Figure 6), explaining and discussing their work while the judges made their decisions about the prize winners.

Session 3: Professor Celine Marmion

Dr **Neville Murphy** (Pau Farras Group, University of Galway/CÚRAM Centre for Medical Device Research) described investigations into intracellular behaviour of metallacarboranes *via* the lens of stimulated Raman spectroscopy (SRS). This work exploits Raman signals of the B-H stretch in the spectrum’s ‘cell-silent’ window, making SRS an ideal candidate for label-free tracking of metallacarboranes and their toxicity. This was contrasted with existing fluorescent multispectral imaging that alters imaging subjects through labelling.

Figure 5. Presentation of gifts to Plenary Speakers: Prof Ramon Vilar and Prof Petra Heffeter

Figure 6. Various delegates at the Poster Sessions (continued overleaf)

Professor **Petra Heffeter** (Medical University of Vienna, Austria) concluded the second session with a plenary talk where she introduced her group's development of new strategies to overcome the therapeutic limitations of

inorganic anticancer drugs, such as resistance and adverse effects. Characteristic conditions of the malignant tumour cell need to be exploited to understand, tune and improve specificity of treatments. She highlighted several key examples of drugs exploiting new strategies. Inhibitors of epidermal growth factor receptors were described, which are activated by cobalt-based prodrugs in hypoxic tumour conditions. Several albumin-targeted therapeutics exploit several conditions, including tumours' enhanced nutrient supply, one of which is in Phase II clinical trials. Preclinical data of Pt(IV) prodrugs were also described in a wide-ranging discussion of an exciting aspect of rational biological inorganic chemistry research.

At the end of the third session, **Dr Amir Abdo** (University of Galway/CÚRAM Centre for Medical Device Research) delivered his IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal 2023 Award Lecture. Dr Abdo gave an excellent talk on metalloporphyrins and their potential as nitric oxide scavengers in the treatment of breast cancer.

Prizes

The **IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal** is awarded annually to one PhD student who has distinguished themselves across a range of criteria throughout their PhD with a focus on research performance, achievements and impact in the field of medicinal and biological inorganic chemistry. Reviewing applications for this competitive award is a highlight of the year for the Society, allowing an opportunity to recognise the breadth of high-achieving final year PhD students or recent graduates whose work aligns to the interdisciplinary aims of IBICS, working across the island of Ireland. The selection committee noted the very high standard of the competition, and before announcing the award they took the opportunity to award **certificates of commendation** to four other applicants for the gold medal: Karolina Wojtczak (University of Galway), Dr Mark Stitch (UCD), Dr Neville

Murphy (University of Galway) and Paul O'Dowd (RCSI). This year's gold medal was awarded to **Dr Amir Abdo** from University of Galway/CÚRAM Centre for Medical Device Research. Amir obtained his MSc in Biological and Bioprocess Engineering from the University of Sheffield (UK) and MSc in Biochemistry from Helwan University (Egypt). After working as a research assistant in radiation chemistry at the National Centre for Radiation Research and Technology (Egypt), he embarked on his doctoral studies at the University of Galway/CÚRAM under the guidance of Professor Abhay Pandit, funded by the College of Engineering and Informatics Scholarship Scheme, and supported by Dr Pau Farràs and Dr Sharon Glynn. Recently, Amir was awarded the Irish Research Council's (IRC) Postdoctoral Fellowship to continue his work on nitric oxide-scavenging compounds and materials for treatment of breast cancer at the University of Galway/CÚRAM.

Figure 7. Photo of Prize Winners, from left: Eleanor Windle (UCD), Joshua Thorogood (TCD), and Ella O'Sullivan (TUD) with Professor Michael Devereaux

Before closing the Symposium, outgoing **IBICS President Professor Michael Devereux** announced the prize-winners selected by judges from the IBICS community during the day. Prizes were awarded to the best poster, best flash presentation and best oral presentation (by a graduate student). The oral presentation prize was sponsored by **IBICS**, the flash prize was sponsored by silver-tier sponsor, the **Institute of Chemistry of Ireland**, and the poster prize was sponsored by **Scientific Laboratory Supplies (SLS)**. All three prize-winners (Figure 3) were presented with a copy of *“Targeted Metallo-Drugs: Design, Development, and Modes of Action”* (Edited by Etelka Farkas & Celine J. Marmion) courtesy of the kind sponsorship of CRC Press – Taylor & Francis Group.

The prize-winners were as follows:

- **IBICS Poster Prize:** Ella O’Sullivan (TU Dublin)
- **ICI Flash Prize:** Joshua Thorogood (TCD)
- **SLS Poster Prize:** Eleanor Windle (UCD)

Figure 8. Local Organising Committee at UCD: Prof. Susan Quinn, Assist. Prof. Joseph Byrne, Sophie Kavanagh, Assist. Prof. Andrew Phillips.

Concluding Remarks

After the prizes, and thanks to all the presenters Prof Devereaux brought the formal scientific proceedings to a close. **Dr Joseph Byrne**, Chair of the Local Organising Committee thanked his co-organisers (Figure 8), chairs (Figure 4) and the IBICS Committee (especially

Professors Devereaux and Howe) for their support during the year preparing the meeting, the sponsors who helped fund the event and exhibited throughout the symposium, and all the postgraduate students at UCD who had contributed on the success of the day

in preparing registration, advertising and keeping things running through the day.

The day concluded with a wine-reception on the balcony of UCD Village, where postgraduate students, academics and other researchers spent the evening networking and discussing the interesting research that had been presented during the course of the Symposium. Next year’s event will take place in University College Cork. Details of symposia past and future, as well as details on other activities and membership of IBICS can be found on the Society’s website www.ibics.ie.

Acknowledgements

The Symposium was made possible by the financial support of several generous sponsors. Support from scholarly organisations was offered by the **Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section** and the **Institute of Chemistry of Ireland**. Commercial sponsors who exhibited on the day were **Mason Technologies, Merck, Accuscience** and **GPE/Julabo**, all of whom are frequent supporters of scientific meetings in Ireland. The Organising Committee are grateful to the IBICS Committee, particularly Mick Devereaux and Orla Howe for organisational support during the preparation of the Symposium and UCD School of Chemistry colleagues for support.

Previous Events in this Series

Programmes of the previous six IBICS Symposia are available at: <http://ibics.ie/ibics-symposia>